

**STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART-III
USE OF ETHYL GALLATE IN COMBINATION WITH
OTHER ANTIOXIDANTS**

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Ethyl gallate in combination with *l*-ascorbyl esters of fatty acids as well as hydrogen gas possesses a very strong antioxidant activity. Destruction of carotene and vitamin-A within the induction period is not appreciable but beyond it they are readily destroyed; the various antioxidants tried afford only very slight protection beyond the induction period.

The marked antioxidant activity of ethyl gallate has already been observed by Lea (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1944, 63, 107). The activity of this substance was also determined with the Swift stability test and the protection factor obtained with butterfat, when used in concentration of 0.005%, was found to be 8.0. In view of the pronounced activity of ethyl gallate, as also of the ascorbyl esters, and the observed behaviour of hydrogen by the present authors (Mukherjee and Goswami, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 239) it was considered necessary to try the various combinations using these substances. The results of storage experiments are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Antioxidant activity with butterfat at 37°.

	Peroxide value after days.					
	15.	30.	45.	60.	90.	120.
1. Control	0.15	0.40	1.8	14.5	31.2	102.0
2. Hydrogen (passed for 2 hours at 50°)	0	0	0.02	0.20	1.0	1.2
3. Ethyl gallate (0.005%)	0	0	0.01	0.16	1.0	1.0
4. Ethyl gallate+hydrogen at 50° for 2 hrs.	0	0	0.01	0.08	0.75	0.70
5. Ethyl gallate+ascorbyl palmitate (0.01%)	0	0	0.01	0.10	0.80	1.0
6. Ethyl gallate+ascorbyl palmitate+ hydrogen at 50° for 2 hrs.	0	0	0.0	0.05	0.40	0.52

From these results it seems that quite desirable results can be observed when suitable combinations are used and the results of these experiments can successfully be utilised commercially. The results of storage experiments in large sealed tins (5 lbs.) for a period of five months are shown below, which definitely indicate the commercial possibilities.

TABLE II

Storage conditions.	Antioxidant.	Peroxide value after 5 months.
1. Hydrogen	—	1.8
2. Hydrogen	Ethyl gallate (0.005%)	1.0
3. Hydrogen	Do +ascorbyl palmitate (0.01%)	1.0

Protective Effect of the Added Antioxidants on the Destruction of Carotene and Vitamin-A in the Oxidation of Butterfat

It has been observed in course of rancidity studies with butterfat (cow) that the yellow colour of the fat is completely bleached on ageing. In this section studies have been made with a view to giving an idea as regards its connection with the development of rancidity in fats and also the rate of destruction of vitamin-A in the butterfat. It is a common observation that fairly old samples of butterfat give negative Carr-Price test. Certain studies have been carried out by Lovern (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1944, 63, 67) in this connection regarding the destruction of vitamin-A in halibut liver oil. Since the vitamin-A content of butterfat is very low, the studies were conducted with samples of butterfat fortified with synthetic vitamin-A in the form of acetate. The rate of deterioration was followed at 40° by blowing air through the molten fat samples, by the determination of peroxide value, and the total amount of carotene and vitamin-A was measured with the help of Lumetron photo-electric colorimeter, using ultraviolet light in the second case and with the proper combination of filters. The experimental results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Peroxide value and destruction of carotene & vitamin-A at 38.5°.

Days of blowing.	Peroxide value.	Carotene (micro g. per 100 g.)	Vitamin-A (I.N.U./g.)	Peroxide value.	Carotene (micro g. per 100 g.)	Vitamin-A (I.N.U./g.)
	Control sample.			With ethyl gallate (0.005%).		
0	0.0	76.8	725	0.0°	76.8	725
1	0.84	76.5	710	0.24	76.8	718
2	1.50	75.9	695	0.84	76.6	715
3	2.20	75.6	680	1.20	76.3	710
4	5.75	43.2	350	1.80	76.0	697
5	6.50	10.0	187	2.20	64.9	675
6	9.4	0.0	120	2.9	58.8	500
7	13.1	0.0	88	6.2	45.0	317
8	18.2	0.0	37.5	8.4	30.2	282
	With ascorbyl palmitate (0.01%).			With ascorbyl palmitate (0.01%) + α -tocopherol (0.005%).		
	0.0	76.8	725	0.0	76.8	725
1	0.25	76.8	715	0.20	76.8	715
2	0.95	76.5	710	0.68	76.6	712
3	1.44	76.0	700	1.00	76.3	710
4	1.76	75.5	688	1.50	76.0	700
5	2.58	75.0	641	1.85	75.7	675
6	4.43	55.4	450	2.40	72.0	600
7	7.0	40.0	335	4.40	58.0	446
8	9.0	25.0	251	6.5	44.0	392

The results of experiments carried out with these antioxidants tend to show that the conservation of vitamin-A and carotene in ghee can very well be achieved by addition of suitable antioxidants. Most pronounced effect has been observed with a mixture of α -tocopherol and ascorbyl palmitate. Ethyl gallate affords a marked protection in as low a concentration as 0.005%. The development of peroxide value and the rate of destruction of carotene and vitamin-A are shown graphically with the control sample in Fig. 1. The results in the table tend to show that the

FIG. 1

loss of carotene or vitamin-A is not appreciable unless a certain peroxide level is attained by the fat, and it may very well be said that during the induction period of the fat, these substances undergo very little changes. Once the induction period is past and rapid oxidation sets in, the vitamin-A and carotene are very rapidly destroyed but still then the antioxidants afford a certain degree of protection outside the induction period.